

SUSTAINABLE FOREST RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE RESILIENCE

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Abstract: Forests are invaluable ecosystems that deliver a wide range of benefits essential to our planet's health and its inhabitants' welfare. This paper examines the forest potential of the Republic of Serbia through the analysis of total forest areas by regions, as well as the impact of logging on these areas and the processes of regeneration. Statistical data from 2019 to 2023 indicate a trend of an increase in total forest area in the Republic of Serbia, but a decrease in afforested areas in certain regions. The research findings underscore the necessity for improved policies and practices in forest management to ensure their sustainability and contribution to global climate change mitigation efforts.

Key words: forests, afforestation, climate change, biodiversity, regional analysis.

1. Introduction

Forests represent a natural potential that provides multiple benefits in all areas of human life. Their importance is especially highlighted nowadays when we face challenges that must be adapted to and overcome on the way to sustainable development. "Forest

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resources and forest lands should be sustainably managed to meet the social, economic, ecological, cultural and spiritual human needs of present and future generations” (Resolution H1: General Guidelines for the Sustainable Management of Forests in Europe; Medarević M., Banković S., Šljukić B., 2008), which is in accordance with the generally accepted definition of sustainable development in all areas.

“Forests cover one-third of the Earth's land mass, serving as a critical pillar for both environmental health and human well-being.” (United Nations) Forests are crucial in the fight against climate change through their natural ability to sequester carbon. This phenomenon, often referred to as forest mitigation, is vital for decreasing greenhouse gas levels in the atmosphere, helping to prevent drastic increases in global temperatures.

The subject of this research is the forest potential of the Republic of Serbia. The *aim of the study* is to analyse the total forest areas by regions in the Republic of Serbia, monitor their logging for economic and energy needs, and assess the process of forest regeneration. The purpose of the research is to highlight the trends in the conservation and expansion of forest potential, which is a crucial resource for enhancing resilience to climate change.

2. The significance of forests for human well-being and resilience to climate change

The forests are home to the highest levels of biodiversity and deliver essential ecosystem services. They provide a wide range of forest-related benefits, some of which can be commercialised, positively impacting social, economic, cultural, spiritual, and health aspects of life. However, nonmarketable and intangible services are often undervalued because many people perceive them as limitless and free. (Raihan, A., 2023) “Forest management should provide, to the extent that it is economically and environmentally sound to do so, optimal combinations of goods and services to nations and local populations. Multiple-use forestry should be promoted to achieve an appropriate balance between the various needs of society.” (Second Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests)

In addition to environmental benefits, forests provide a wealth of resources, such as timber, food, and medicine, which are crucial for the livelihoods of millions of people worldwide. They also serve as a shelter for biodiversity, supporting countless species of plants and animals, many of which are yet to be discovered. Moreover, forests are vital sources of drinking water for nearly half of the world's largest cities, illuminating their importance in sustaining human life and daily activities. “A very important contribution is the possibility of accessing forests for recreational purposes and the cultural and spiritual values of individual forest sites. Forests and forestry represent one of the main pillars of sustainable rural development.” (Medarević M., Banković S., Šljukić B. 2008) The cultural significance of forests for indigenous communities cannot be overstated, as they hold spiritual value and are often integral to traditional ways of life.

The contribution of the forestry sector to employment is also important, as is the significant role of wood in providing energy in total energy consumption. “Forests provide employment and generate income for millions of people worldwide. Many types of jobs depend on forests and their resources, from loggers and construction workers to trekking guides and forest rangers. While we all depend on forests in one way or another, it is estimated that about 350 million people around the world live within or near forests and

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are *highly* dependent on them for their livelihoods. This includes millions of indigenous people who are almost entirely dependent on forests for their subsistence and survival.” (Brajcich, K, 2021)

To protect and sustainably manage these irreplaceable ecosystems, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) spearheads global initiatives aimed at forest conservation. Their efforts are particularly pertinent in the face of deforestation, which continues to pose a significant threat to both environmental and social stability. By promoting sustainable practices that engage local communities and stakeholders, UNEP seeks to secure a healthier future for both people and the environment. (United Nations)

The role of forests extends far beyond carbon sequestration. They act as critical buffers against extreme weather conditions, including storms and floods, thereby safeguarding communities from the impacts of climate change. Understanding the significance of forests in the pursuit of a sustainable future is essential, particularly concerning the ambitious goal of limiting global warming to 1.5°C. (United Nations) Achieving this target is impossible without substantial contributions from forests, which can be accomplished by halting deforestation and improving forest management practices, along with afforestation initiatives. “The mitigation potential of forests, estimated between 4.1 and 6.5 GtCO₂ by 2030, highlights their indispensable role in meeting international climate goals. Forest conservation, sustainable management, and restoration practices offer a cost-effective means of climate mitigation, potentially accounting for up to 30% of the available mitigation measures over the next decade.” (United Nations)

Forests are natural places that store carbon. How we treat them can either help or worsen the climate crisis. “Each year, the world’s forests absorb 16 billion metric tons of CO₂ – that’s more than 40% of global fossil fuel emissions. However, if forests are destroyed, then they can actually worsen climate change by releasing more carbon than they absorb” (Brajcich, K, 2021)

Forests have become more important lately because of rising economic needs, the need to tackle climate change, and growing worries about protecting the environment. “Currently, forests are exposed to more recurrent and intense disturbances strongly influenced by climate.” (Vacek, Z., Vacek, S., Cukor, J., 2023)

The role of trees is very important in city areas. “Climate change threatens the health and survival of urban trees and the various benefits they deliver to urban inhabitants.” (Esperon-Rodriguez, M., Tjoelker, M.G., Lenoir, J. *et al.* 2022) As temperatures rise and extreme weather events become more frequent, these trees face increased stress from heat, drought, and storms. This jeopardises their role in improving air quality, providing shade, and enhancing urban aesthetics. Without proper care and adaptation strategies, many urban trees may struggle to thrive in changing conditions, which could lead to a decline in green spaces and the valuable ecosystem services they offer. Cities need to invest in tree preservation, adopt climate-resilient planting practices, and develop urban forestry programs that prioritise the health of these vital organisms. By doing so, we can ensure that urban trees continue to support our communities and contribute to a healthier, more sustainable urban environment.

Many countries are implementing extensive afforestation initiatives to enhance environmental conditions in degraded or challenging areas. China's Three Northern Protected Forest Program (TNSFP), which covers 42.40% of the country's total land area, is

currently the largest afforestation project in the world. (Zhai, J., Wang, L., Liu, Y., Wang, C., Mao, X. 2023)

The loss of biodiversity, climate change, and global warming are connected to social progress and the well-being of people (Raihan, A. 2023). As ecosystems deteriorate and species become extinct, the essential services they provide, such as clean air, fresh water, and food security, are compromised, directly impacting communities and their quality of life. Addressing these intertwined issues is crucial for creating sustainable development strategies that promote ecological health while enhancing the resilience and quality of life for all people.

2. Analysis of forest areas by regions in the Republic of Serbia

a) Analysis of the total forest area in the Republic of Serbia and regions

In the Republic of Serbia, according to data for 2023, the total forest area was 2.8 million ha. (Table 1) It is important to note that in the period from 2019 to 2023, this forest area expanded by slightly more than 27%. This represents a positive result in the expansion of the forest fund, especially since 2022.

Table 1. Total forest area in the Republic of Serbia (ha)

Year	Covered forest area, total, ha
2019	2.237.511
2020	2.261.386
2021	2.261.386
2022	2.261.386
2023	2.854.955

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

Figure 1 shows the trend in the logging timber volume of broadleaf and coniferous forests in the period from 2019 to 2023. The annual logging timber volume of broadleaf forests presents variations, ranging from 2.7 million m³ (2020) to 3.3 million m³ (2022). Regarding coniferous forests, the logging annual timber volume is fairly uniform and shows a slight trend of a decrease by about 8% in 2023 compared to 2019.

Figure 1. Logging timber volume of broadleaf and coniferous trees in the Republic of Serbia

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

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In Figure 2, it is presented that the largest forest areas are in the regions of Šumadija and Western Serbia and Southern and Eastern Serbia. The regions of Vojvodina and Belgrade have only 8% of the total forest areas. Region of Šumadija and Western Serbia covers 44% of the total forest fund, while the region of Southern and Eastern Serbia predominantly participates with 48% in the total forest areas of the Republic of Serbia.

Figure 2. Covered forest area by regions in the Republic of Serbia, 2023 (ha)

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

From 2019 to 2023, it is observed that areas under forests have been significantly expanded in all regions, except the Belgrade Region. In the Belgrade Region total forested area has declined in the analysed period by about 13%. In the Region of South and Eastern Serbia total forest area has increased by 27%, and in the Region of Šumadija and Western Serbia by 29%. The highest increase in forest area is noticed in the Vojvodina Region, by more than 30%.

Table 2. Total forested areas (ha) by regions in the Republic of Serbia (2019-2023)

Year/Region	Belgrade Region	Vojvodina Region	Region of Šumadija and Western Serbia	Region of South and Eastern Serbia
2019	61.987,21	131.452,90	980.213,35	1.063.857,54
2020	62.037,84	138.584,26	988.495,99	1.072.267,91
2021	62.037,84	138.584,26	988.496,00	1.072.268,00
2022	62.037,84	138.584,26	988.495,99	1.072.267,91
2023	53.850,66	171.746,12	1.271.244,91	1.358.114,06
Changes (%) 2023/2019	-13,13	30,65	29,69	27,66

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

b) Analysis of the logging timber volume in the Republic of Serbia and regions

It is important for the analysis in this paper to consider the **logging timber** volume (Table 3). Similar to the analysis of forested areas by regions, the logging timber volume is highest in the regions of Šumadija and Western Serbia, as well as Southern and Eastern Serbia.

Table 3. Logging timber volume by regions in the Republic of Serbia in the period 2019-2023 (m³)

Region	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Belgrade Region	102.574	102.797	78.543	91.984	71.705
Vojvodina Region	664.639	649.613	735.648	832.019	798.787
Region of Šumadija and Western Serbia	1.402.113	1.311.455	1.257.495	1.356.823	1.245.867
Region of South and Eastern Serbia	1.201.864	1.116.362	1.283.747	1.457.731	1.226.950

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

However, it is noted that the largest increase in the logging timber volume was recorded in the Vojvodina Region, by as much as 20% in 2023 compared to 2019. (Figure 3). An increase in logging timber volume has been noticed in the Region of South and Eastern Serbia, as well. In the Belgrade region, a decrease in the logging trees in 2023 compared to 2019 of about 30% is recorded. There is also a positive trend in the reduction of the logging trees in the Šumadija and Western Serbia regions of about 11%.

Figure 3. Logging timber volume by region in the Republic of Serbia in the period 2019-2023. (m³)

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

b) Analysis of the afforested area in the Republic of Serbia and regions

In addition to logging timber volume, it is important to analyse and monitor **afforested areas**. Data on afforested areas in the Republic of Serbia has significantly decreased in 2023 compared to 2019. In 2019, 3.077,99 ha were afforested, while in 2023 only 1.728,38 ha were afforested. The smallest afforested area was in 2021, at only 1.203 ha.

Table 4. Afforested areas in the Republic of Serbia in the period from 2019 to 2023 (ha)

Year	Total forested area, ha
2019	3.077,99
2020	1.482,00
2021	1.203,00
2022	1.364,87
2023	1.728,38

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

The trend of afforestation in the Republic of Serbia is visible in Figure 4, where a decline in afforested areas is observed up to 2021. However, in the subsequent period until 2023, there is an increase in the number of hectares that have been afforested.

Figure 4. Afforested areas in the Republic of Serbia in the period from 2019 to 2023 (ha)

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

Regionally, the largest area is being afforested in the Vojvodina and Šumadija and Western Serbia regions. This is followed by the Southern and Eastern Serbia region and the Belgrade region. However, there is a tendency for afforested areas to decrease year by year. The most drastic decline in afforestation is in the Šumadija and Western Serbia region and in the Belgrade region. In 2023, compared to 2019, a decrease in afforested areas was recorded in the Šumadija and Western Serbia region by over 68%, and in the Belgrade region by over 65%. In the same analysed period, a decrease in afforested areas was recorded in the Vojvodina region by around 20%, while in the Southern and Eastern Serbia region 16% less area was afforested in 2023 than in 2019. (Table 5)

Table 5. Total afforested areas by regions in the Republic of Serbia in the period 2019-2023 (ha)

Region/Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Belgrade Region	68,48	35,20	20,26	28,23	23,52
Vojvodina Region	1039,36	607,52	469,39	553,96	824,43
Region of Šumadija and Western Serbia	1471,52	507,85	397,43	483,12	462,86
Region of South and Eastern Serbia	497,64	331,43	316,00	299,56	417,57

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

Figure 5 clearly shows a sharp decline in afforested areas from 2019 to 2021, followed by a slight increase until 2023.

Figure 5. Total afforested areas by region in the Republic of Serbia in the period 2019-2023 (ha)

Source: Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Municipalities and Regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

Results of the analysis of logging forest timber and afforested areas by regions show that in the Belgrade region, there is a trend of significant decrease in afforestation of areas, along with a yearly reduction in the volume of logging trees. Thus, the total area under forests in this region is decreasing, which is a consequence of insufficient afforestation of the areas. In the Region of Vojvodina, the trend is to increase the logging trees yearly, with a slight decrease from 2022. The afforested areas, the largest concerning all regions, certainly contributed to the largest increase in total areas under forests in Vojvodina region. The region of Šumadija and Western Serbia recorded the largest decrease in logging trees, along with stagnation in the afforestation of areas. The region of Southern and Eastern Serbia has a trend of decreasing afforested areas yearly. A bad trend is that in the period up to 2022, a decrease in afforested areas was recorded, while during the same period, an increase in logging trees was observed. In 2023, there was an increase in afforested areas, but also a decrease in logging trees in this region.

3. Conclusion

Forests play a crucial role in offering essential ecosystem services, including conserving soil and water, regulating the climate, and storing carbon. Aspects of the importance of forests in biodiversity conservation, climate regulation, and the provision of ecosystem services are relevant for Serbia, where forests face challenges such as climate change.

The analysis in this paper shows the key role of forests in the ecological and economic framework of the Republic of Serbia. Although there are regional differences, the observed decline in forested areas, such as in the Belgrade region, indicates an urgent need for improved forest management practices and policies.

The analysis highlights the significant importance of forests in the Republic of Serbia for both environmental health and economic stability. The data from 2019 to 2023 shows a concerning decline in afforested areas, particularly in the regions of Šumadija and Western Serbia, where afforested land has decreased by over 68%, compared surfaces in 2023 and 2019. This trend points to an urgent need for effective forest management practices and policies to stop further losses and promote regeneration.

The findings emphasise the necessity of implementing strategies such as sustainable logging practices, increased investment in afforestation, and community engagement in forest conservation. By prioritising these actions, Serbia can enhance biodiversity, improve air quality, and strengthen its natural carbon sinks, which are vital in the fight against climate change.

To ensure forests continue providing essential ecosystem services, policymakers must adopt a comprehensive approach that includes monitoring and evaluation of forest health and incentives for landowners to maintain and expand forested areas. Sustainable forest management and effective afforestation strategies are necessary to strengthen ecosystem resilience and preserve biodiversity. Ultimately, taking decisive action now will not only protect Serbia's natural resources but also support the well-being of its people and contribute to global efforts to mitigate climate change.

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Literature

- Raihan, A. (2023) A review on the integrative approach for economic valuation of forest ecosystem services, *Journal of Environmental Science and Economics*, ISSN: 2832-6032, <https://doi.org/10.56556/jescae.v2i3.554>
- Second Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe 16-17. June 1993, Helsinki/Finland, Resolution H1: General Guidelines for the Sustainable Management of Forests in Europe .

- Medarević M., Banković S., Šljukić B. (2008) *Sustainable forest management in Serbia - state and potentials. Bulletin of the Faculty of Forestry*, 97: 3356.
- United Nations, Why do forests matter? <https://www.unep.org/topics/forests/why-do-forests-matter>
- Brajcich, K (2021) 14 Reasons Why Forests Are Important, Sustainable Travel International, <https://sustainabletravel.org/14-reasons-why-forests-are-important/>
- Medarević M., Banković S., Šljukić B. (2008) *Sustainable forest management in Serbia - state and potentials. Bulletin of the Faculty of Forestry*, 97: 3356.
- Vacek, Z., Vacek, S., Cukor, J. (2023) European forests under global climate change: Review of tree growth processes, crises and management strategies, *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 332, ISSN 0301-4797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.117353>.
- Esperon-Rodriguez, M., Tjoelker, M.G., Lenoir, J. *et al.* (2022) Climate change increases global risk to urban forests, *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 12, 950–955. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01465-8>
- Zhai, J., Wang, L., Liu, Y., Wang, C., Mao, X. (2023) Assessing the effects of China's Three-North Shelter Forest Program over 40 years, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 857, Part 1, ISSN 0048-9697, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159354>.)
- Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2020, Municipalities and regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade.
- Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2021, Municipalities and regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade.
- Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2022, Municipalities and regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade.
- Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2023, Municipalities and regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade.
- Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2024, Municipalities and regions in the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade.

ODRŽIVO UPRAVLJANJE ŠUMSKIM RESURSIMA U KONTEKSTU OTPORNOSTI NA KLIMATSKE PROMENE

Rezime: Šume su neprocenjivi ekosistemi koji pružaju širok spektar koristi neophodnih za zdravlje naše planete i dobrobit njenih stanovnika. U ovom radu se sagledava potencijal šuma Republike Srbije kroz analizu ukupnih šumskih površina po regionima, kao i uticaj seče drveća na ukupne površine i procese obnavljanja šumskog fonda. Statistički podaci od 2019. do 2023. godine ukazuju na trend povećanja ukupne šumske površine u Republici Srbiji, ali smanjenja pošumljavanja površina u određenim regionima. Rezultati istraživanja naglašavaju potrebu za unapređenjem politika i praksi gazdovanja šumama kako bi se osigurala njihova održivost i doprinos naporima za ublažavanje globalnih klimatskih promena.

Cljučne reči: šume, klimatske promene, biodiverzitet, regionalna analiza.